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CURRENT STATE AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY

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Abstract. This article examines the main approaches to organizing production, sales, and marketing activities. It highlights issues related to maximum capacity utilization, mass production, centralized distribution of essential resources, labor productivity control, and meeting specific needs of society. The article emphasizes that enterprises should produce only those goods, and in such quantities, that can be consumed by society.

Keywords: enterprise, production, resource, product, market, innovation.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются основные подходы к организации производства, сбыта и маркетинговой деятельности. Освещаются вопросы максимального использования производственных мощностей, массового производства продукции, централизованного распределения важнейших ресурсов, контроля производительности труда и удовлетворения конкретных потребностей общества. В статье подчеркивается, что предприятиям необходимо производить только те товары и в таком количестве, которое может быть потреблено обществом.

Ключевые слова: предприятие, производство, ресурс, товар, рынок, инновация.

INTRODUCTION

In today's market economy, the efficient operation of all economic entities is achieved through reducing and optimizing costs. This, in particular, depends on the logistics costs of manufacturing enterprises and the proper, efficient functioning of logistics systems.

Business analysis is necessary to optimize logistics management processes and improve their practical outcomes. A key factor in this regard is the specific nature of industrial markets, since each B2B market has its own distinctive characteristics.

Today, our country's economy is developing rapidly. This is largely due to the fact that all sectors of the economy are producing goods and services based on development strategies and effectively using the country's existing potential. In this process, particular attention is being paid to industrial enterprises and to accelerating their access to international markets through industrial production.

The gradual economic development of any country requires passing through certain stages. For a country seeking to strengthen its economy, industrialization serves as an important foundation for socio-economic development. Industrial development in Uzbekistan creates a basis for the growth of many sectors and industries. The rational organization of the national economy remains one of the key priorities of economic policy. Effective use of the natural, economic, and labor potential of the regions is an important prerequisite for achieving sustainable economic growth, strengthening economic independence, and improving the standard of living of the population.

Enhancing regional potential plays an important role in economic development and in improving the functioning of its structural components. Therefore, development projects should be designed on the basis of each region's economic potential in order to meet the needs of industry, manufacturing, processing, and services.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. M. Mirziyoyev dated August 15, 2024, No. PP-295¹, "On Additional Measures to Further Increase the Industrial Potential of the Regions," is also aimed at increasing industrial capacity and ensuring the socio-economic development of the regions.

1 <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/7069809>

LITERATURE REVIEW

An analysis of the existing literature on marketing shows the need to improve modern marketing principles, brand promotion methods, and flexible approaches to consumer requirements. In his textbook on marketing strategies, R. G. Ibragimov states: "Marketing strategy is understood as the use of a model of enterprise behavior in the market, established for a certain period of time. With its help, the enterprise seeks to ensure its success."

Many economists and scholars have contributed to the development and implementation of marketing strategies. Among them are such well-known researchers as F. Kotler, David Aaker, Clayton Christensen, Seth Godin, Kevin Keller, Byron Sharp, and Jay Baer.

Although research conducted in the field of marketing in our country over many years has been based on national characteristics, it is also necessary to acknowledge the scholars who have made a significant contribution to the development of marketing theory. These include R. Ibragimov, Y. Abdullaev, A. Saliev, M. Sharifkhodjaev, D. Rakhimova, Sh. Ergashkhodjaeva, Sh. Musayeva, and others.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The study employed a systematic approach, marketing analysis, benchmarking, and digital metrics. Data from social media platforms were collected and analyzed using large-scale observation methods.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

A procedure has been established to accelerate industrial development in the regions, promptly address existing problems faced by enterprises, and further improve the effectiveness of cooperation between local government bodies and industrial sectors. In this regard, the position of Chief Industrial Development Specialist has been introduced in district and city departments of economy and finance. The main purpose of this measure is to expand opportunities for entering international markets through industrial development, study the challenges faced by industrial enterprises, and strengthen institutional support in this process. The implementation of this procedure at the local level is expected to contribute to increased productivity, improved product quality, higher sales volumes, and greater investment activity in the industrial sector.

Further improvement of industrial efficiency and competitiveness can be achieved through the accelerated and sustainable development of the country's industrial sectors, expansion of their export potential, technical and technological re-equipment of manufacturing enterprises, supply of the domestic market with products produced by local enterprises, efficient use of available resources, and implementation of an active investment policy.

Overall, industry is one of the key sectors of the national economy. It differs from other sectors by the volume of added value it creates, its role in meeting the needs of the population, and its high level of production dynamism. Industrial development ensures the stable growth of the national economy. Diversification processes in industry are being improved through the processing of extracted and cultivated resources, food production, development of new products, and expansion of product range and assortment.

Industry is one of the fundamental sectors of the country's national economy. It represents the primary and leading sphere of material production, and its development largely determines the sustainable growth of the national economy. Sustainable development of industrial sectors is achieved through the introduction of modern equipment and technologies into production, as well as structural modernization.

One of the important areas of structural transformation in the national economy is modernization of the industrial complex. The main objective of the country's structural policy is to strengthen the competitiveness of Uzbekistan's economy through structural reforms in industry (Table 1).

Table 1
Statistics on the dynamics of industrial development in the Republic of Uzbekistan (2018–2025)²

Klassifikator_ru	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024
Industrial production	235340.7	322535.8	368740.2	456056.1	553265	658991.7	880198.5
Mining and quarrying	29087.9	43438.9	33106.9	43872.2	52093.5	55442	70248.2
Manufacturing industry	189642.6	254860.9	305928.6	378186.4	460491.8	556382.4	745094.4
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning supply	14518.5	22014.7	27375.3	30815.5	37653.7	43967.6	59934.3
Water supply; sewerage, waste collection and disposal	2091.7	2221.2	2329.3	3182	3026.1	3199.7	4921.5
Food production	25256	35337.3	42314.9	48643.3	57547.3	65678.2	102732.6
Beverage production	4948.9	6402.5	7417.6	10135.4	16111.3	17986.4	24118.1
Tobacco production	1490.8	1743.8	1951.2	2089.4	2888.9	3200.2	4516.4
Textile manufacturing	24835.2	29946.6	36713.9	52372.3	62850.7	71509.8	89489
Clothing production	7732.2	9165.8	10402.4	13592.8	17264.8	23087.8	31906.8
Production of leather and related products	1647.9	1588.8	1616.9	2083.9	2220.6	2795.7	4137.1
Manufacture of wood and cork products (except furniture), straw products and wickerwork materials	1600.6	1596	1563.8	2209	2537	2144.2	3360.9
Production of paper and paper products	1633.5	1942.8	2257.8	2896.2	4275.6	5701.3	8821.6
Printing and playback of recorded materials	1260.3	1361.9	1081.5	1683.2	2627.5	2217.7	3359.7
Production of chemical products	5589.3	9964.2	11003.3	11371.5	16095.9	25082.2	30757.1
Production of coke and petroleum products	15078.4	18974.3	21213.5	28080.7	33639.5	33838	40220.3
Production of basic pharmaceutical products and preparations	1612.4	1945.8	2543.5	3903	3402	4005.5	4874.7
Production of rubber and plastic products	5295.4	5347.8	7017.7	8463.3	9342.7	11056.2	17140.3
Production of other non-metallic mineral products	12190.3	13721.8	16287.7	20714.8	22442.4	28460	42129.5
Metallurgical industry	31299.5	57327.3	79445.1	96785.5	107071.9	126485.7	171299.9
Manufacture of finished metal products, except machinery and equipment	5093.8	5628.8	7063.3	11064.1	12584.3	14404.1	17319.7
Production of computers, electronic and optical products	1040.5	2001.6	3457.7	6232.9	6261.7	4202.3	4543.4
Manufacturing of electrical equipment	6985.3	7373.3	8635.4	11212	14388	18702	25252
Manufacture of machinery and equipment not included in other categories	3504.5	4373	4291.3	4353.3	5448.7	5643	8347
Production of motor vehicles, trailers and semi-trailers	26631.3	33091.2	33594.9	32167.6	51396.2	76904.9	87106.7
Manufacture of other transport equipment	504.8	818.3	879.3	1137.6	1520.7	1734.5	2279.4
Furniture production	1694.9	2299.1	2097.3	3059.8	3996.7	4278	7904.7
Production of other finished goods	1363.7	1523.3	1699.3	2049.5	2499.1	4203.5	7423
Repair and installation of machinery and equipment	1353.1	1385.8	1379.4	1885.3	2078.4	3061.2	6054.8

² <https://stat.uz/uz/>

The table shows stable and significant growth in Uzbekistan's industrial sector from 2018 to 2024. Industrial output increased nearly 3.7 times, reflecting dynamic economic modernization, capacity expansion, and investment growth.

The highest growth was observed in manufacturing, metallurgy, textiles, automobile production, and food production. Significant increases in these sectors indicate a gradual shift of the economy toward higher-value-added goods and expanded export opportunities.

Some industries, including furniture, paper, chemicals, and pharmaceuticals, also demonstrated notable growth rates, indicating diversification of the industrial sector.

Steady growth in electricity supply, water supply, rubber and plastics production, and non-metallic mineral products reflects infrastructure development and increasing demand from the construction and manufacturing sectors.

Thus, Uzbekistan's industrial sector demonstrated comprehensive and stable development during 2018–2024, strengthening its role in the national economy and creating a foundation for future innovation and investment growth.

Tobacco products account for the largest share, at 23 percent, indicating their dominant role in the production structure. Textile production, at 12 percent, and food production, at 14 percent, also make significant contributions. More modest but stable sectors include clothing production at 6 percent, paper production at 4 percent, as well as polymers, chemicals, and other industries.

Smaller segments, ranging from 1 to 2 percent, include furniture manufacturing, printing, rubber products, mineral products, finished metal components, and related industries.

Overall, the figure confirms the diversity of the industry's sectoral composition and shows which areas occupy leading positions and which have a relatively smaller share (Table 2).

Table 2

Dynamics of production volumes, investment volumes in the industry and exports in 2020–2024 at the enterprises of the O'zto'qimachilik sanoat association³

Name of the indicator	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	Growth in 2024 compared to 2020	
						(+;-)	%
Volume of production in comparative prices	17248.8	21991.2	33025.1	39101.7	41607.3	+24358.5	+2.41 times
Cotton yarn	575.2	629.8	862.3	905.0	932.4	+357.2	+162.1
Finished thread yarn	268.3	406.0	716.2	810.0	930.7	+662.4	+3.47 times
Knitted fabric	111.2	119.6	203.8	240.0	275.8	+164.6	+2.48 times
Her sewing and knitwear products	432.0	548.1	1,997.8	1380.0	2691.0	+2259.0	+5.23 times
Hosiery	197.3	257.0	450	460.0	742.0	+577.7	+3.76 times
Export	1541.3	1868.4	2945.2	3300.0	3400.0	+1857.7	+2.2 times
Investments	832.3	712.9	733.2	771.2	730.3	-102	-12.25

Information on the dynamics of innovation and investment activities of the "O'zto'qimachilik sanoat" Association for 2010–2024 is presented in Table 2. The results of the data analysis show that the number of innovation and investment projects implemented in the textile industry during the study period did not follow a uniform trend. From 2020 to 2024, the number of projects generally tended to increase, reaching 65 in 2020 and 86 in 2023. However, in 2024, the number of innovation and investment projects amounted to 44.

Changes in the value of innovation and investment projects during the study period also varied. In particular, in 2020, this indicator amounted to USD 829.7 million, while the highest value was recorded in 2024, reaching USD 836.3 million. In the context of globalization, where increasing attention is paid to the environmental friendliness of products, significant modernization processes are taking place in the textile industry.

3 [O'zto'qimachilik sanoat – "O'zto'qimachilik sanoat" uyushmasi](#)

The current stage of textile industry development differs from previous stages in its focus on sustainable and environmentally friendly production. This is primarily reflected in fiber production.

Globally, demand is increasing for materials made from bamboo, eucalyptus, corn, soy, seaweed, and other natural sources. The advantage of these fibers is that they are environmentally friendly and biodegradable.

Another important trend is the use of recycled materials. Many manufacturers are increasingly focusing on recycled polyester, which can be produced from plastic bottles and other waste materials. Global brands are also expanding the use of such fibers in their products in order to reduce the amount of plastic waste released into the environment.

Furthermore, manufacturers have begun using bacteria to produce artificial silk and bio-nylon. These materials are known as biotech fibers. In addition, many countries are introducing new methods that allow producers to save water in cotton cultivation.

Spinning mills are increasingly using modern automated systems. New spinning machines are equipped with quality sensors and can automatically adjust yarn tension and speed, thereby reducing defects.

The production of functional yarns is also improving. Such yarns may combine antibacterial properties, temperature regulation, and moisture-wicking functions. They are most commonly used in the production of medical and sportswear.

Another increasingly popular trend in yarn production is blended yarn. It combines natural and synthetic fibers. This production method improves the quality of products made from such yarn, making them stronger, softer, more elastic, and more durable.

Due to modernization and the introduction of high-tech equipment, the weaving industry is developing rapidly. Most manufacturers are switching to shuttleless looms, which ensure high-quality production in a shorter time. In addition, these looms generate less noise and weave threads more precisely.

One of the main trends in this field is the production of ultra-fine fabrics. Advances in microfiber technology allow manufacturers to produce lightweight and durable materials used in everyday clothing and outerwear.

Particular attention is being paid to the creation of smart textiles that can change their properties depending on external conditions, such as becoming more breathable, water-repellent, or providing UV protection. Some manufacturers are also introducing smart technologies that integrate electronic components into fabrics.

Modern digital design systems help reduce waste and improve pattern accuracy.

3D knitting is one of the innovations rapidly developing the knitwear industry. This technology helps reduce waste and accelerate the production process.

In addition, many new brands have begun using functional, breathable knitwear. This type of knitwear may have antibacterial properties and can help cool or warm the body. In line with green economy principles, many manufacturers are also recycling yarn, which helps produce goods with minimal environmental impact.

In recent years, the garment industry has been developing rapidly due to the introduction of new technologies and production methods. One of the key trends is the automation and robotization of production processes. Robots help reduce defects and improve production efficiency.

Online retail is contributing to the development of on-demand manufacturing, where clothing is produced according to customer demand or specific orders. This method helps reduce waste and minimize excess inventory.

One of the most important environmental trends is zero-waste design, which involves creating patterns that allow fabric to be used as efficiently as possible, without unnecessary scraps.

Technical textiles are one of the fastest-growing areas of the textile industry. They are widely used in medicine, construction, transportation, sports, and industrial safety. Smart textile materials capable of measuring body temperature, heart rate, and activity levels are particularly advanced in this field.

In addition, materials with special properties are developing rapidly. These include fire-resistant, acid-resistant, and ultra-strong fabrics used for workwear and protective clothing.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The analysis demonstrates that the modern textile industry is increasingly oriented toward innovation, sustainability, and operational efficiency. Across all stages of the value chain—from fiber production to the manufacture of finished goods—there is a growing adoption of digital technologies, automation, advanced production systems, material recycling, and environmentally responsible solutions. These developments contribute to higher productivity, improved product quality, and enhanced competitiveness in both domestic and international markets.

In light of these findings, it is recommended to further accelerate the introduction of innovative technologies, expand the use of sustainable and recycled materials, strengthen investment in research and development, and support the digital transformation of textile enterprises. Particular attention should also be given to energy-

efficient production methods, workforce skill development, and the expansion of high-value-added textile products. The implementation of these measures will contribute to the sustainable development of the textile industry and strengthen its position in the global market.

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